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A framework for building climate storylines based on downward counterfactuals: the case of the European Union Solidarity Fund

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34 **Abstract**

35 Recent research introduced the concept of climate storylines as an alternative approach to
36 estimate climate impact and better deal with uncertainties. A climate storyline is an event-based
37 approach which aims at building “*physically self-consistent unfolding of past events, or of*
38 *plausible future events or pathways*”. As such, climate storylines may profit from downward
39 counterfactual thinking, which aims at analyzing how past events could have been worse.
40 Notwithstanding the various applications of downward counterfactual thinking in the natural
41 risk management literature, no study relates this with the climate storyline approach. The main
42 goal of this paper is thus to introduce a framework that supports the development of climate
43 storylines from downward counterfactuals. The framework is event-oriented, it focuses on
44 impact, and it is participatory-based. We apply it to study the impact of tropical cyclones
45 affecting the European Union’s outermost regions on the European Union Solidarity Fund. We
46 find that payouts to the outermost regions can hamper a recovery of the fund should a major
47 event happen in mainland Europe. To avoid this also considering future changes, an increase
48 in capitalization up to 100 % percent may be required.

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52 **Keywords:**

53 Climate storylines; Downward counterfactuals; European Union Solidarity Fund;

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74 1. Introduction

75 The increasing need for climate adaptation policies is raising interest within the climate
76 research community about the most appropriate use of climate data and impact models when
77 supporting decision-making under deep uncertainty. Within this debate, Hazeleger et al.
78 (2015), Shepherd et al. (2018), Shepherd (2019) and Sillmann et al. (2020) challenged the
79 conventional probabilistic approach of modeling uncertainty in regional climate that generates
80 local climate information by downscaling results from global climate model ensembles
81 simulations. Such probabilistic modelling approach, also referred-to as a “top-down approach”,
82 has been considered inadequate in dealing with uncertainties in regional climate predictions
83 because it mingles together aleatoric and epistemic uncertainties (Shepherd, 2019).

84 As an alternative, Shepherd et al. (2018) introduced the *climate storyline* approach, where a
85 *storyline* is defined as “*a physically self-consistent unfolding of past events, or of plausible*
86 *future events or pathways*”. Unlike the conventional probabilistic approach, the climate
87 storyline approach does not aim at predicting system states nor at assigning probabilities to
88 these states. Rather, the storyline approach focuses on identifying what *plausible* factors (i.e.,
89 climatic and socio-economic) bring the system under severe stress. Furthermore, instead of
90 using ensembles of model simulations, climate storylines aim at describing and understanding
91 (series of) individual regional climate events. Thus, the climate storyline approach is well-
92 suited also to study compound climate risk, namely risk rising from the interaction of several
93 weather or climate events (Zscheischler et al. 2020; 2018).

94 Shepherd et al. (2018) identified four main strengths of the storyline approach. First, it
95 improves people’s risk awareness as it triggers episodic memory, i.e., it reproduces climate
96 events that are similar to those people already experienced and can thus personally relate to.
97 This aspect is relevant as it allows one to account for people’s perception of risk, based on
98 cultural and personal values, and thus connects with the narratives of change approach to
99 climate risk governance advocated by Krauß (2020) and Krauß and Bremer (2020). Second, it
100 strengthens decision-making as it focuses on revealing the factors responsible for system
101 failure, thus allowing the identification of robust decision options, i.e., options which perform
102 satisfactorily under a wide range of system states (McPhail et al. 2018; Wilby and Dessai 2010).
103 Third, it allows to partition uncertainties relative to thermodynamic and dynamic aspects of
104 climate events, which are instead merged when using the conventional probabilistic approach.
105 Last, it enables the exploration of the boundaries of plausibility, i.e., visualizing and estimating
106 the full spectrum of plausible impacts that can arise from the considered climate events.

107 The first point above is most effective if storylines are event-based and hence connect to events
108 people can relate to. Therefore, the climate storyline approach may benefit from counterfactual
109 thinking, which refers to imagining alternative pasts by reconstructing events that could have
110 occurred but actually did not (Roese 1999). Roese (1999) distinguishes between upward and
111 downward counterfactuals to refer to events which may have turned better or worse than they
112 actually did, respectively. As downward counterfactuals aim at considering plausible negative
113 outcomes, they trigger the so-called wake-up call, i.e., a motivation to change and improvement
114 (McMullen and Markman 2000). Woo (2019) and Woo, Trevor and Seria (2017) propose to
115 adopt a downward counterfactual thinking approach to address risk analysis problems. They
116 recognize that historical events are just one realization of many possible alternatives and show
117 that, when considering downward counterfactuals of these historical events, many disasters
118 that took societies by surprise could have been anticipated.

119 Applications of downward counterfactual thinking in the context of natural disaster risk include
120 a counterfactual analysis of the 1999 Kocaeli earthquake (Woo and Mignan, 2018), the 1997
121 Montserrat Volcanic explosion (Aspinall and Woo, 2019) and flood risk (Zischg and
122 Bermúdez, 2020). Methods to derive plausible counterfactuals vary greatly, including
123 historical analysis, Bayesian Networks, and perturbation of past events. Lin et al. (2020)
124 propose a general framework on how to generate downward counterfactuals and apply this to
125 various extreme natural events. Regardless of the adopted approach, the greatest challenge
126 when building downward counterfactuals of past events is ensuring plausibility.

127 As the storyline approach and risk studies using downward counterfactuals thinking have so
128 far developed along complementary, yet very distinct, research lines, the first goal of this paper
129 is to combine the two into a single framework. The framework is iterative and aims to foster
130 co-production of knowledge between scientists and stakeholders when developing storylines,
131 and, as such, resembles previously introduced approaches for creating climate risk narratives
132 (Jack et al. 2020). In particular, the framework first allows one to construct climate storylines
133 based on an iterative analysis of what (combinations of) counterfactuals are deemed critical
134 (i.e., downward), and to then analyze the future impact of storylines using climate change and
135 socio-economic scenarios. The value of combining counterfactuals and scenarios is also
136 recognized by Derbyshire (2020) and Schoemaker (2020) who discuss, within a more general
137 context, how counterfactual reasoning enhances scenario-building and thus allows better
138 planning. In our framework, the aforementioned challenge of plausibility when modeling
139 downward counterfactuals is addressed by simulating counterfactual events using past

140 ensemble forecast data, which, by their own nature, represent physically plausible alternatives
141 of past weather and climate events.

142 The second goal of the paper is to apply the proposed framework on a case study. To this end
143 we study the implications of tropical cyclones on the financial capacity of the European Union
144 Solidarity Fund (EUSF), a fund set-up in 2002 to provide financial relief to European Union
145 Member States affected by large disasters following natural hazards. In particular, as previous
146 studies analyzed the impact on the EUSF of events occurring within mainland Europe
147 (Hochrainer, Linnerooth-Bayer, and Mechler 2010), the goal is to build climate storylines to
148 assess whether, and to what extent, tropical cyclones affecting the EU's outermost regions, i.e.,
149 French, Portuguese and Spanish islands located outside mainland Europe, can compromise the
150 stability of the EUSF.

151 The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 illustrates the proposed framework; Section 3 is
152 split into three subsections introducing the case study, the impact model, and data; Section 4
153 presents results; Section 5 critically discusses the framework and results; Section 6 provides
154 final remarks.

155 2. Building climate storylines: a downward counterfactual approach

156 This section introduces the proposed framework of building climate storylines using downward
157 counterfactuals. The main challenge when constructing downward counterfactuals is ensuring
158 plausibility, which is paramount to avoiding arbitrary and fictional speculations of the past and
159 to ensuring trust of the stakeholders regarding the formulated storylines. A way to ensure
160 plausibility without resorting to new modeling or detailed historic investigations is by using
161 past numerical weather forecast data, especially ensembles (Palmer 2019). Although these data
162 were generated to serve a different purpose, i.e., to quantify the uncertainty of a weather
163 prediction (Leutbecher and Palmer 2008), they do represent, when used retrospectively,
164 physically plausible realizations of past weather events to the degree that numerical weather
165 forecast models capture the underlying physical processes. Using numerical weather forecasts
166 of tropical cyclones allows one to identify historical near-misses that could have been
167 catastrophic. For example, according to forecasts, Hurricane Matthew could have been one of
168 the most destructive hurricanes in Florida had it made landfall at Palm Beach as a Category 4
169 hurricane in 2016, Hurricane Irma with a less westerly track would have struck Miami as
170 Category 4 in 2017, and Hurricane Dorian could have struck Florida as a Category 4 storm in

171 2019 (Woo, Trevor, and Seria 2017; Woo 2019). These alternative tracks were all physically
172 plausible and could have led to much higher damages than the actual events did.

173 The proposed framework is composed of three steps and it is illustrated in Fig. 1. In the first
174 step, impact is assessed based on all available counterfactuals. In other words, an impact model
175 is run using each ensemble forecast member for the period of interest. As the figure shows, for
176 each year and each event within a year, there are several possible counterfactuals. As one
177 cannot easily identify which ones are critical a priori, it is thus crucial to assess impacts for
178 each of them. In the second step, climate storylines are built from (a combination of)
179 counterfactuals while making sure that each event in each storyline is represented by only one
180 of its counterfactual representation. This step needs to be carried out iteratively and
181 participatorily for two main reasons. First, the potential number of climate storylines that can
182 be built from counterfactuals is very large, while in practice only a limited number of
183 meaningful storylines is required. This calls for a refinement procedure that iteratively builds
184 storylines and adjusts them based on different counterfactuals. Second, identifying what
185 (combinations of) counterfactuals are of particular interest for the problem at hand can only be
186 defined after agreeing upon what constitutes bad system performances, be it e.g. simply high
187 damages to the local communities, severe indirect consequences, or – as for the problem
188 addressed in the present work and later introduced in Section 3 - potentially lasting effects on
189 capital availability. It further matters what kind of events more strongly relate to people's
190 experience, e.g. if single large events, compound events, or a combination thereof. This can
191 only be achieved through participation and engagement of all parties involved. Finally, after
192 building climate storylines, possible future impacts are estimated based on projections of
193 climatic, socio-economic, and policy scenarios. This step can either be accomplished by
194 applying climatic and socio-economic scenarios with the aim of assessing the temporal
195 evolution of risk, or by assessing plausible future impacts via a *what-if* or exploratory analysis.
196 In the latter case, the goal is to estimate what combinations of changes in the drivers lead to
197 concerning system states and, only after and if needed, understand *when* such changes can
198 occur in the future (Bankes, Walker, and Kwakkel 2013).

199

200 *Fig. 1* The proposed framework to build climate storylines based on downward counterfactuals. The
 201 hierarchical structure reported in the first step resembles the one of forecast data. Each event in each
 202 given year has multiple counterfactuals (cntrf for short), with e.g. $cntrf_{njq}$ being the q^{th} counterfactual
 203 of the j^{th} event of the n^{th} year. In step 2 storylines are built from combining downward counterfactuals.
 204 The selected counterfactuals in the figure are examples. Finally, in step 3, $Proj_Storyline_s$ represents
 205 the future projection of the s^{th} storyline given the applied scenarios. The framework is introduced with
 206 an annual temporal resolution, but different resolutions can easily be adopted.

207 **3. Case study**

208 We applied the framework introduced in Section 2 to assess the impact of tropical cyclones
 209 affecting the outermost regions of European Union’s (EU) Member States on the financial
 210 sustainability of the European Union Solidarity Fund (EUSF). The EU’s outermost regions
 211 include French territories (Réunion and Mayotte in the South-West Indian Ocean; French
 212 Guiana, Saint Martin, Guadelupe, Martinique in the North Atlantic Ocean) and the
 213 Macaronesian Region consisting of Portuguese (Madeira, Azores) and Spanish (Canary
 214 Islands) islands.

215 **3.1 The European Union Solidarity Fund (EUSF)**

216 The EUSF was set up in 2002 in response to severe floods in Central Europe to provide
 217 financial relief to Member States affected by natural disasters. Although its main structure and
 218 objectives have remained unchanged since 2002, the EUSF underwent several reforms in 2014
 219 (Hochrainer-Stigler, Linnerooth-Bayer, and Lorant 2017). Until 2013, the EUSF was
 220 capitalized with 1 billion EUR per year, payouts were triggered if damages exceeded a

221 threshold of either 0.6% of the countries' Gross National Income (GNI) or 3 million EUR in
222 2002 prices, and financial aid amounted to 2.5% of the damage below the threshold, plus 6%
223 of the damage above it. Even when the damage threshold was not met, the EUSF could still be
224 used for smaller "extraordinary regional disasters" if the disaster were deemed to have long-
225 lasting effects on the region's economic and social stability (Hochrainer, Linnerooth-Bayer,
226 and Mechler 2010). However, since no clear guidance was provided, major regional disasters
227 were evaluated case-by-case, where 45 out of 61 requests for financial aid to regional disasters
228 were rejected or withdrawn (Hochrainer-Stigler, Linnerooth-Bayer, and Lorant 2017).
229 Consequently, one of the major changes of the 2014 reforms was a clearer definition of
230 "extraordinary regional disasters".

231 After 2013, regional disasters were explicitly defined as disasters leading to regional damages
232 of more than 1.5% of the regional GDP for NUTS 2 territories (from the French *Nomenclature*
233 *des unités territoriales statistiques*), and more than 1% of the regional GDP for the EU's
234 outermost regions. Financial aid for regional disasters amounts to 2.5% of the total damage.
235 All previous payout rules for national disasters remained unchanged, with the 3 million EUR
236 threshold updated to 2011 prices. Capitalization rules also changed, with a new annual
237 capitalization of 500 million EUR in 2011 prices (thus about one half of the previous annual
238 capitalization amount) with the option of carrying forward for one year any unspent capital.

239 Fig. 2 shows the EUSF data of historical payouts and the calculated capital availability given
240 these payouts and the capitalization rules for the period 2002-2018. Overall, no significant
241 contribution from the outermost regions was registered as a consequence of tropical cyclones,
242 as only two payouts took place, in 2007 and 2017, and they were both very low compared to
243 overall payouts. Interestingly, the capital level dropped below zero in 2017 after a large
244 earthquake that took place in Central Italy. To cope with this, upfront payments from the year
245 2018 were made. Although the outermost regions contributed to render overall payouts in 2017
246 even higher due to payments to Saint-Martin and Guadalupe after Hurricanes Irma and Maria,
247 their overall absolute contribution was very low as the EUSF capital would have dropped below
248 zero anyway.

249 Historic evidence thus suggests that tropical cyclones affecting the outermost regions cannot
250 undermine the EUSF capital capacity. However, the available data cover a too short time frame,
251 also considering that until 2014 there were no clear payout rules in place for regional disasters.
252 We thus aim to better study this aspect by building climate storylines through analyzing
253 payouts from counterfactual tropical cyclones. Following the EUSF payout rules introduced

254 above, estimating counterfactual payouts to the outermost regions is straightforward after
 255 direct damages from counterfactual tropical cyclones are estimated. This requires the use of an
 256 impact model, which is introduced in the next subsection.

257

258 *Fig. 2 Historical payout data (bars, left y-axis) and calculated EUSF capital (lines, right y-axis) for the*
 259 *2002-2018 period in million Euros. Yellow bars indicate payouts due to tropical cyclones affecting the*
 260 *outermost regions and blue bars all other payouts. The solid line indicates the calculated EUSF capital*
 261 *including all payouts and the dashed black line the EUSF capital with payouts to mainland Europe*
 262 *only. The horizontal dashed red line indicates zero capital levels.*

263 3.2 The impact model

264 Direct economic damages from tropical cyclones are estimated using the open- source and -
 265 access CLIMADA impact model described in detail in Aznar-Siguan and Bresch (2019).
 266 Briefly, direct damages in CLIMADA are assessed as a function of weather-related hazard,
 267 exposure of people and goods to such hazards, and vulnerability of the exposed entities. Hazard
 268 from tropical cyclones is represented in CLIMADA by a map of the 1-min sustained wind
 269 gusts, modelled as the sum of two components: a static circular wind speed and a translational
 270 wind speed arising from the tropical cyclone movement. Both components are derived from
 271 information about tropical cyclones tracks such as time, location, radius of maximum winds,
 272 and central pressure. More details can be found in Geiger, Frieler and Bresch (2018).
 273 CLIMADA provides various built-in methods to generate exposure (see, e.g., Aznar-Siguan
 274 and Bresch, 2019; and Eberenz et al. 2020). We use the one introduced in Gettelman et al.
 275 (2018) where the exposed economic value is calculated by downscaling regional Gross
 276 Domestic Products (GDP) using nighttime lights data. Vulnerability in CLIMADA is

277 represented as typically done in natural catastrophe models, i.e., via an impact function which
278 relates the hazard intensity to a damage percentage in exposed value.

279 3.2 Data

280 Hazard data about historic tropical cyclone tracks are retrieved from the International Best
281 Track Archive for Climate Stewardship (IBTrACS) dataset (Knapp et al. 2010). Counterfactual
282 tropical cyclones are simulated by using forecast data provided by the Observing System
283 Research and Predictability Experiment (THORPEX). THORPEX initiated in 2005 the
284 THORPEX Interactive Grand Global Ensemble (TIGGE) program, which contains many
285 forecasting data sets of tropical cyclone tracks from several international meteorological
286 agencies (Swinbank et al. 2016; Park, Buizza, and Leutbecher 2008). The dataset contains
287 historical tropical cyclone track data since 2008 and is updated continuously. We also perform
288 a probabilistic assessment using synthetic tropical cyclone tracks of the STORM dataset
289 (Bloemendaal et al. 2020) for the sake of comparison and to estimate the 200-y and 1000-y
290 payouts.

291 Regarding exposure, we use as nightlight data the DMSP-OLS Nighttime Lights Time Series
292 (Lloyd 2016) provided by NOAA until 2013 and the NASA's Black Marble data (Román et al.
293 2018) after 2013. Regional GDP data are taken from EUROSTAT
294 (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>). Finally, the adopted vulnerability function is provided by
295 Eberenz, Lüthi, and Bresch (2020) who calibrated impact functions for each tropical cyclone
296 basin by comparing modeled and reported damages. They carried out calibrations using
297 different methods and we here use the one they derived optimizing the total damage ratio.

298 4. Results and discussion

299 As a proof of concept of the approach presented in Section 2, in this section we assess whether,
300 and to what extent, EUSF payouts to the EU outermost regions due to downward counterfactual
301 tropical cyclone events may compromise the stability of the fund. We present results following
302 the steps in the proposed framework. As introduced in Section 2, the selection of climate
303 storylines based on downward counterfactuals needs to be based on inputs from stakeholders.
304 Given the proof-of-concept nature of the case study, however, we do not conduct a
305 participatory analysis and build climate storylines based on various (combinations of)
306 downward counterfactuals that can compromise the stability of the EUSF capital, i.e., lead to
307 persistent negative capital levels.

308 3.3 Assess impact from the full set of counterfactuals

309 We present results in terms of payouts to the outermost regions (top panel of Fig. 3) and the
 310 resulting capital (bottom panel of Fig. 3). In particular, we compare data about historic payouts,
 311 simulated historic payouts (i.e., using the CLIMADA impact model with IBTrACS) and the
 312 counterfactuals payouts (i.e., using the CLIMADA impact model with TIGGE forecast data).
 313 Given these payouts and those registered in mainland Europe in the same years (blue bars in
 314 Fig. 2), capital is calculated accordingly.

315
 316 **Fig. 3** Payouts to the outermost regions (top) and capital (bottom). The top figure reports data about historic
 317 payout (orange star), simulated historic payouts (yellow bars) and counterfactual payouts (boxplot). For the
 318 latter, boxplots show the interquartile range and the median value. Maximum counterfactual payouts are also
 319 shown as a green diamond. The lighter blue dotted line shows the 200-year payout, while the darker blue dotted
 320 line shows the 1000-year payout. The bottom figure shows (in analogy to Fig. 2) capital calculated with data of
 321 historic payouts (solid orange line), with simulated historic payouts (solid yellow line), and the worst possible
 322 outcome (dark green line), i.e. cumulating each event's max counterfactual payout. The horizontal dashed red
 323 line indicates zero capital levels.

324 When comparing historic payouts data and simulated historic payouts (orange and yellow stars
 325 in the top panel of Fig. 3), one can see that the model correctly simulates only one payout in
 326 2017 but it underestimates its extent. When comparing capital resulting from historic payouts
 327 data and simulated historic payouts (orange and yellow lines in the bottom panel of Fig. 3), the
 328 capital resulting from the latter overestimates capital from the former, but the difference
 329 between the two is almost negligible. Given the large uncertainties in impact modeling
 330 (Wagenaar et al. 2016) and the fact that we are only simulating wind-driven damage, the

331 underestimation (overestimation) of payouts (capital) can arguably be considered acceptable.
 332 The adopted set-up of the CLIMADA impact model is thus suited to simulate impacts from
 333 counterfactuals.

334 Looking at the counterfactual payouts (boxplots in the top panel of Fig. 3), it is evident that
 335 many more payouts than historically witnessed could have happened, and with higher
 336 magnitude. Maximum counterfactual payouts (green diamonds in the top panel of Fig. 3) are
 337 large in the years 2011, 2017 and 2018, with e.g., this latter that could have registered a payout
 338 higher than the 200-y payout. To establish whether payouts to the outermost regions can
 339 undermine capital availability, we calculate capital resulting from the worst possible
 340 counterfactual realizations, i.e., cumulating each event's max counterfactual payout (green line
 341 in the bottom panel of Fig. 3). It emerges that payouts to the outermost regions alone cannot
 342 bring EUSF capital levels below zero. For example, the counterfactual year 2011 requires large
 343 payouts, but the EUSF capital is still of about 600 million EUR. Rather, when large losses
 344 occur in mainland Europe, as in 2017 after the earthquake in Central Italy, large payouts to the
 345 outermost regions could exacerbate that loss and, most importantly, prevent a recovery of the
 346 capital in the following years.

347 By focusing on counterfactuals in the years 2017 and 2018, the following section first aims at
 348 identifying which of these cause the missed recovery (i.e., the downward counterfactuals) and
 349 at comparing them to the corresponding historic events. Then, based on these, climate
 350 storylines are built.

351 **Table 1** Simulated historic and downward counterfactual events leading to EUSF payouts in 2017 and 2018. The
 352 first number in parenthesis indicate damage in million EUR, and the second number indicates payouts in million
 353 EUR. The reported damages and payouts of the historic events are simulated with CLIMADA using IBTrACS.
 354 Data about historic damages and payouts from Irma and Maria together report 1'956 million EUR and 48.9
 355 million EUR.

Historic		Counterfactuals	
2017	2018	2017	2018
Irma (320 - 8)	-	Irma (250 - 6.2)	Berguitta (12'971 - 324)
Maria (335 - 8.4)		Maria (2'472 - 62)	Fakir (929 - 23.2)
		Harvey	Isaac

		(95 - 2.3)	(354 - 8.86)
		Carlos (1'494 - 37.3)	Helene (58.7 - 1.46)
		Enawo (6'090.8 - 152.2)	Kirk (144.2 - 3.6)
		Ophelia (68.7 - 1.7)	Leslie (328 - 8.2)
			Ava (256 - 6.4)

356

357 3.4 Build climate storylines from downward counterfactuals

358 As reported in Table 1, historically, payouts to the outermost regions were triggered after
359 Hurricanes Irma and Maria in 2017 and no payouts were triggered in 2018. Counterfactually,
360 instead, there could have been more payouts in 2017 than those triggered by Hurricanes Irma
361 and Maria, as well as payouts in 2018. To illustrate this point, we compare the historic and
362 downward counterfactual events (Fig. 4). One can see that most of the outermost regions
363 (islands in yellow) are within a red-shaded zone, meaning that winds from the downward
364 counterfactual are higher than the observed winds. This can be explained either by a change of
365 the track and/or the intensity of the tropical cyclone.

366 Tropical cyclone Enawo is an example where a change in track would have mattered more than
367 a change in intensity (top left panel of Fig. 4). Enawo was a Category 4 tropical cyclone that
368 had a devastating impact on Madagascar but a negligible one on Réunion, as it passed far away
369 from the latter. Counterfactual Enawo, however, would have had a lower intensity (Category
370 2) while taking a more southward path, thus passing very close to Réunion leading to
371 substantial losses. Counterfactual Enawo leads to the highest counterfactual payout in 2017.

372 Tropical cyclone Berguita is an example where change in intensity could have mattered more
373 than change in track (top right panel of Fig. 4). Berguita was a tropical storm that affected both
374 Mauritius and Réunion as it passed close to these islands. Counterfactual Berguita would have
375 passed closer to Réunion, almost making landfall, and with a much higher intensity, i.e., as a
376 Category 3 tropical cyclone. Counterfactual Berguita leads to the highest counterfactual
377 payout in 2018. Tropical cyclone Leslie is an example where both a change in intensity and path

378 would have mattered to make the event worse from the perspective of the outermost regions
 379 (Figure 4 bottom right). Leslie was a Category 1 tropical cyclone that passed very close to
 380 Madeira and then made landfall in mainland Portugal leading to high damages and losses.
 381 Counterfactual Leslie would have had a more northward track hitting the Azores as a Category
 382 2 hurricane.

383
 384 **Fig. 4** Observed (solid line) and downward counterfactual (dashed line) tropical cyclone tracks and wind field
 385 difference (colour shading, m/s) between the two (counterfactual minus observed). Red (blue) areas indicate
 386 higher winds from the downward counterfactual (observed) events. Line colours indicate categories of the Saffir-
 387 Simpson scale. Each panel in the plot reports the tropical cyclone's name, basin and year. The outermost regions
 388 are indicated in yellow.

389 The identified downward counterfactuals serve as building blocks for climate storylines. Four
 390 climate storylines are identified and summarized in Table 2. The storylines are of increasing
 391 impact and built to represent impacts from single large events and event series (i.e., compound
 392 events). Compound events are analyzed in the form of temporal clustering, i.e., multiple
 393 weather events affecting the same territories within the same season (Zscheischler et al. 2020).
 394 In modeling event series, it is reasonable to assume that after an event hits, the damage potential

395 of the following events decreases. This is taken into account by reducing each event’s damage
 396 by an amount equal to the fraction of GDP lost from the preceding event.

397 **Table 2** *The four identified climate storylines: the rationale behind their choice, a description relative to the*
 398 *impact on the EUSF and the involved downward counterfactuals.*

Climate storylines			
	Rationale	Description	Downward counterfactuals
First	One high-impact event	A single large payout is required to Réunion in 2018.	2018: Berguitta
Second	One high-impact event per year	Two large payouts are required to Réunion in 2017 and 2018.	2017: Enawo 2018: Berguitta
Third	One high-impact event in one year followed by a series of events the next year	A single large payout is required to Réunion in 2017, followed by a series of payouts to Réunion, the Azores, Guadalupe, Saint-Martin, and Martinique in 2018.	2017: Enawo 2018: Berguitta, Fakir, Isaac, Helene, Kirk, Leslie, Ava
Fourth	A series of events per year	A series of payouts are required to Réunion, the Azores, Guadalupe, Saint-Martin, and Martinique in 2017 and in 2018.	2017: Carlos, Enawo, Harvey, Irma, Maria, Ophelia 2018: Berguitta, Fakir, Isaac, Helene, Kirk, Leslie, Ava

399
 400 EUSF capital availability resulting from the four climate storylines is reported in Fig. 5. The
 401 increase in severity from the first to the fourth storyline is clear. However, there is only little
 402 difference between EUSF capital under the second and third storylines, meaning that the
 403 additional damage contribution of the event series in 2018 is not substantial. The figure also
 404 shows where the climate storylines locate with respect to the range of downward

405 counterfactuals delimited by historic payouts (upper bound) and the worst possible scenario
 406 (lower bound), as introduced in Fig. 3. Although to different degrees, all storylines prevent a
 407 recovery of the EUSF capital after the payouts to the earthquake in Central Italy in 2017. The
 408 next section investigates how impact from these climate storylines might change under
 409 climatic, socio-economic, and policy scenarios.

410

411

412 **Fig. 5** Capital from the four identified climate storylines (blue, orange, green and purple solid lines), the range
 413 of counterfactual outcomes (light blue bandwidth) and the level of zero capital (dotted red line).

414 **4.3 Projection of climate storylines into the future**

415 Following the proposed framework, impacts of the selected climate storylines are projected
 416 into the future by evaluating the climate storylines under various assumptions of climatic,
 417 socio-economic, and policy changes. In particular, we follow a bottom-up approach where
 418 future changes are explored in a *what-if* analysis fashion. The goal is to estimate under what
 419 plausible future states of the world the EUSF undergoes severe budget deficits without aiming
 420 to quantifying when such states may occur, nor how likely they are.

421 In terms of climatic changes, an increase in the intensity of tropical cyclones is expected. The
 422 degree of such change is however uncertain. Knutson et al. (2020) estimated that the range of
 423 change of maximum surface wind speed is between 1 and 10 percent, which is the range we
 424 consider. As for socio-economic change, we assume an increase in GDP from 1 to 20 percent.
 425 As for policy changes, they are modeled as increase in EUSF capitalization, which we assume
 426 spans from 1 to 150 percent. As the fund was indeed capitalized with 1 billion EUR before 2013
 427 (thus about twice as much as the current capitalization), an increment up to 150 percent is
 428 considered reasonable and affordable.

429

430 **Fig. 6** 3D-heatmaps of simulated capital for the four selected climate storylines (see Table 2 for details). Panels
 431 on each row indicate climate storylines, while panels on the columns indicate the years 2017 and 2018 projected
 432 in a hypothetical future. The axes in each panel indicate percentage increases of tropical cyclones (TC) intensity,
 433 Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and annual EUSF capitalization levels. Blue (red) colours indicate capital above
 434 (below) zero.

435 Under the first climate storyline (first row of Fig. 6), a slight increase in capitalization (at about
436 30 percent) would allow the fund to cope with the highest modeled increases in tropical cyclone
437 intensity and GDP. As this storyline simulates a single large downward counterfactual in 2018,
438 it seems that no single large event to the outermost regions can be of concern for the EUSF
439 capital. The second and third storylines (second and third rows of Fig. 6) do not substantially
440 differ from each other (as it also emerged from Fig. 3). For these storylines, an increase in
441 capitalization of about 50 % would allow to cope with high climate and socio-economic
442 increases. The fourth climate storyline (last row of Fig. 6) simulates series of downward
443 counterfactuals for two consecutive years. The effect of the temporal cumulation is evident
444 when looking at capital levels in the second year, where acceptable levels of capital (light blue)
445 can be found at around 80 % increase in capitalization and a 100 % increase in capitalization
446 is required to cope with the highest climatic and socio-economic scenarios considered. A 100
447 % percent increase in capitalization implies re-introducing the capitalization rules in force
448 before the 2013 reforms.

449 Restoring the previous capitalization rules would thus guarantee that the contribution of the
450 outermost regions will at most exacerbate large payouts coming from mainland Europe (Year
451 1) but would not prevent a recovery from such year. From a general perspective, however,
452 Hochrainer, Linnerooth-Bayer, and Mechler (2010) concluded that, even before the 2013
453 reforms, the EUSF might have been undercapitalized against flood losses within mainland
454 Europe. Therefore, a substantial policy change in how the EUSF is capitalized would be needed
455 to cope with payouts from both the outermost regions and continental Europe.

456 5. Discussion

457 In this section we comment upon the advantages and limitations of the introduced framework,
458 as well as discuss limitations of the case study results. As for the framework, we identify one
459 challenge and one limitation. The challenge relates to the requirement of selecting a limited
460 number of climate storylines from many (combinations of) counterfactuals based on inputs
461 from experts, practitioners, and other interested parties. This entails iteratively visualizing the
462 impact of (combinations of) downward counterfactuals and agreeing upon the ones deemed
463 critical and relevant for the case study and by all parties involved. If, on the one hand, this
464 aspect is indeed the strength of the approach, as it guides stakeholders through a process of
465 system understanding and awareness about how things could have gone worse, it does, on the
466 other hand, certainly require more resources and efforts than a standard probabilistic analysis.

467 The limitation regards the poor support of the proposed framework to *a posteriori* statements
468 about the likelihood of the identified climate storylines. Although avoiding to model
469 probabilities is indeed an explicit goal of the climate storylines approach, in some cases there
470 could be the need to assign probabilities *after* climate storylines are built. One possible way to
471 remedy this is by interpreting the built climate storylines as causal networks in a Bayesian
472 framework (Shepherd 2019).

473 In terms of results, the main limitations relate to the limited amount of payout data from the
474 outermost regions against which we were able to compare simulations from the impact model.
475 Indeed, the impact model rightly simulates a payout in 2017 and within the correct order of
476 magnitude, but more data would have helped to better benchmark the model. Another limitation
477 relates to the use of GDP as a proxy of asset values. Although this was convenient as EUSF
478 payouts for the outermost regions are triggered based on how direct damages relate to GDP,
479 not all GDP relate to physical assets, and therefore this may be a poor proxy of asset exposure.
480 Finally, TIGGE forecast data are biased and are known to underestimate tropical cyclone
481 variables like central pressure and maximum wind speed (Li, Wang, and Peng 2016; Na et al.
482 2018; Knaff et al. 2010). Therefore, counterfactual damages and payouts, all else being equal,
483 might have been underestimated.

484 6. Conclusions

485 In this paper we introduce a framework for building climate storylines based on downward
486 counterfactuals and apply it to a proof-of-concept case study. The framework is event-oriented,
487 focuses on impact, and is participatory-based. It entails three steps. First, impact is assessed
488 from all counterfactuals. Second, climate storylines are built in an iterative process as a
489 (combination of) downward counterfactuals. Last, the identified climate storylines are
490 projected in the future based on climate, socio-economic and policy scenarios. We apply this
491 framework to assess the impact of tropical cyclones affecting the EU outermost regions
492 (French, Spanish, and Portuguese islands) on the sustainability of the European Union
493 Solidarity Fund, a fund set-up by the EU in 2002 to help Member State to cope with natural
494 disasters.

495 Results of this proof-of-concept study show that the contribution of the outermost regions alone
496 cannot compromise the availability of the EUSF capital. However, should a major event occur
497 in mainland Europe and large payouts to the outermost regions be required in the same year,
498 the latter would hamper a recovery of the EUSF capital. Future projections show that a 30 %

499 increase in capital would allow coping with a single large event. Should large payouts to the
500 outermost regions happen in consecutive years and from event series, however, an increase in
501 capitalization from 60 % to 100 % may be required, which would imply restoring the
502 capitalization rules that were in force before 2013.

503 The adopted framework allows visualizing the (downward counterfactual) weather events
504 responsible for critical outcomes and to investigate under what climatic, socio-economic, and
505 policy scenarios these can be controlled or exacerbate further. The introduced framework
506 explicitly avoids any probabilistic statement regarding neither the likelihood of the events
507 deemed critical nor the applied scenarios. However, in some cases it can nevertheless be
508 relevant for decision makers to be able to assign probabilities to such events and scenarios.
509 Future research will focus on this aspect by, e.g., interpreting climate storylines as causal
510 networks as well as applying the framework to a wider range of climate risk management
511 problems.

512

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